

1 Article

2 **Reduced Cycle Spinning Method for the** 3 **Undecimated Wavelet Transform**

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9 **Abstract:** The Undecimated Wavelet Transform is commonly used for signal processing due to its
10 advantages over other wavelet techniques, but it is limited for some applications because of its
11 computational cost. One of the methods utilised for the implementation of the Undecimated
12 Wavelet Transform is the one known as Cycle Spinning. This paper introduces an alternative Cycle
13 Spinning implementation method that divides the computational cost by a factor close to 2. This
14 work develops the mathematical background of the proposed method, shows the block diagrams
15 for its implementation and validates the method by applying it to the denoising of ultrasonic
16 signals. The evaluation of the denoising results shows that the new method produces similar
17 denoising qualities than other Cycle Spinning implementations, with a reduced computational
18 cost.

19 **Keywords:** cycle spinning; undecimated wavelet transform; computational cost; denoising;
20 ultrasonic.

21 **1. Introduction**

22 The wavelet transforms are commonly used to analyse non-stationary signals and, as a result,
23 there is a wide bibliography both generalist [1-4] and applied [5-7]. The wavelet term is assigned to a
24 set of time frequency transforms that depending on the selection of some parameters produces more
25 specific definitions of wavelet transforms. The most utilised wavelet is the Discrete Wavelet
26 Transform (DWT), which has the disadvantage of not being shift-invariant. The Undecimated
27 Wavelet Transform (UWT) was designed to overcome the lack of the DWT time variance [8]. There
28 are several implementations of the UWT, for instance the a'trous algorithm [8], but this work deals
29 with the technique called Cycle Spinning (CS) [9].

30 The CS method has been used in the processing of different kinds of images: astronomical
31 images [10], synthetic aperture radar images [11], medical images for diagnosis [12] and for
32 estimation of fluid flows [13], or the classic image of Lena [14]. But CS has been also used for the
33 extraction of signal characteristics from electrical discharges [15], for denoising in electromagnetic
34 signals from geophysical explorations [16] or for denoising of ultrasonic signals used both for
35 nondestructive evaluations [17, 18] and for medical diagnosis [19, 20].

36 The CS algorithm has some advantages over other wavelet implementations. The main
37 advantage is that the final processed signal is obtained by the combination of different shifted
38 versions of the processed signal. This characteristic produces a high redundancy of the processed
39 information and allows different points of view, which can suggest different solutions, for instance
40 the best basis selection in wavelet denoising problems. The redundancy of the processed
41 information is intrinsic to the UWT, but the CS UWT technique is more redundant than other UWT
42 techniques. For instance, the a'trous algorithm generates $(J + 1)$ wavelet coefficients per sample

43 whereas the CS algorithm generates 2^J (being J the maximum decomposition level of the UWT
44 analysis) [18].

45 The UWT CS analysis is based on performing numerous DWT's to circular shifted versions of
46 the signal to process, generating the CS coefficients. After the wavelet coefficients processing, the
47 UWT CS synthesis is carried out performing several inverse DWT's (iDWT), resulting in a set of
48 recovered signals that must be combined to obtain the final processed signal. The limitation of the
49 CS method is the high number of DWT's and iDWT's to perform, and the reduction of the CS
50 computational cost has been treated in several works. In [21, 22] was demonstrated that the CS
51 coefficients, obtained performing DWT's with maximum decomposition level J , were periodic every
52 2^J shifts. Recently in [18] the complete formulation of the CS coefficients was done and other
53 periodicities of the CS coefficients were showed. These periodicities allowed the proposal of some
54 alternatives to reduce the computational cost in the CS method. One of them was the Partial Cycling
55 Spinning (PCS) method [17, 19] that performs the CS method using only a subset of the circular
56 shifted versions of the signal to process, reducing the number of DWT's and iDWT's.

57 The present work introduces an improvement to the CS UWT implementation by the removing
58 all the iDWT's except one, reducing the computational cost. The improvement is obtained doing a
59 combination of the wavelet coefficients, after the Digital Signal Processing (DSP) tap and previously
60 to the iDWT tap. By this way, the combination is performed over the wavelet coefficients instead of
61 over the recovered signals, reducing the number of iDWT's to one. Figure 1 shows the schemes of
62 the standard CS method and the proposed Reduced Cycle Spinning (RCS) method.
63

64
65 **Figure 1.** Cycle Spinning method and the proposed Reduced Cycle Spinning method.

66 This work develops the mathematical formulation of the new RCS method, studies its
67 advantages and limitations, evaluates different options for the wavelet coefficients combination and
68 shows experimental results which validate the proposed method. The experimental validation is
69 done by comparing the RCS method with the CS and the PCS methods applied to the denoising of
70 ultrasonic signals. This paper is written in four parts: Section 2 resumes the CS method; Section 3
71 introduces the new RCS method; Section 4 describes the simulations of an ultrasonic denoising
72 problem and Section 5 explains the conclusions.

73 2. Undecimated Wavelet Transform and Cycle Spinning

74 The Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) is defined by:

$$DWT_{x(k)}(j, n) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{k=\infty} x(k) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^j}} \psi\left(\frac{k}{2^j} - n\right) \quad j, n \in Z \quad (1)$$

75 where $x(k)$ is the discrete signal, $\psi(k)$ the mother wavelet, n is the discrete time and j is the scale
76 level.

77 The popularity of the DWT is in part due to its easy implementation with iterative filter banks
78 using the Mallat algorithm [23]. In Mallat algorithm the input signal passes through two filters (a
79 low pass filter and a high pass filter) and the outputs of the filters are decimated. The output of the
80 high pass filter is formed by the wavelet coefficients and the output of the low pass filter is the input

81 of the filtering level 2, which uses the same filter bank as the level 1. Repeating this
82 filtering-decimating process, the wavelet coefficients are obtained for all the decomposition levels.

83 Figure 2 shows the Mallat DWT analysis algorithm. The input $X(z)$ is the z-transform of $x(k)$,
84 $G(z)$ and $H(z)$ are the transfer functions of the low pass and high pass filters, the blocks with $(2\downarrow)$
85 represent the decimation by 2, $d_j(z)$ are the wavelet coefficients at the decomposition level j and
86 $a_j(z)$ are the coefficients from the output of low pass filter of level J .

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Figure 2. DWT Mallat analysis algorithm with J levels.

90 The number of wavelet coefficients obtained by the Mallat algorithm is coincident with the
91 number of samples of the input signal $x(k)$, K samples. The expressions of the DWT coefficients are
92 [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} d_j(z) &= X(z)[H(z)(2\downarrow)]^{j-1}[G(z)(2\downarrow)] \\ a_j(z) &= X(z)[H(z)(2\downarrow)]^j \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

93 The synthesis of the signal from the wavelet coefficients can be obtained using another filter
94 bank, where two new low and high filters, $\tilde{G}(z)$ and $\tilde{H}(z)$ (obtained from $G(z)$ and $H(z)$), are
95 utilized and where the decimator is replaced by an interpolator. The expression of the recovered
96 signal is:

$$\tilde{X}(z) = a_j(z)[(2\uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^j + \sum_{j=1}^J d_j(z)(2\uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2\uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} \quad (3)$$

97 The DWT is not a shift-invariant transform because the wavelet coefficients of level j are
98 calculated with periods of 2^j samples [8]. To overcome this problem was developed the
99 Undecimated Wavelet Transform (UWT) that is an invariant-shift transform [8].

$$UWT_{x(k)}(j, n) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{k=\infty} x(k) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^j}} \psi\left(\frac{k-n}{2^j}\right) \quad j, n \in Z \quad (4)$$

100 There are two widely used algorithms for the implementation of the UWT: the a'trous
101 algorithm [8] and the CS method [9]; the relationship among them was studied in [18].

102 The CS algorithm is based on the DWT's of several circular shifted versions of the input signal
103 $x(k)$. Thus, it is necessary to calculate a DWT for each shifted version of the input signal. The shifted
104 versions of the input signal, $x_m(k)$, are obtained using the shift operator $Sh_m[\]$ [18].

$$x_m(k) = Sh_m[x(k)] = x((k+m)_{\text{mod } K}) \quad \text{being } (k+m)_{\text{mod } K} = \begin{cases} (k+m+K) & \text{if } (k+m) < 0 \\ (k+m) & \text{if } 0 \leq (k+m) < K \\ (k+m-K) & \text{if } (k+m) \geq K \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

105 with $0 \leq k \leq K-1$ and $0 \leq m \leq M-1$, being m the shift and $M \leq K$. $M = 2^J$ because the CS
106 UWT coefficients are periodic every 2^J shifts [21, 22], thus if M is increased the wavelet coefficient
107 obtained are periodically repeated.

108 In the z -transform domain the shift operator $Sh_m[\cdot]$ is transformed to $S_m[\cdot]$ and the shifted
109 signals can be expressed as:

$$X_m(z) = TZ\{Sh_m[x(k)]\} = S_m[X(z)] = \text{Remainder} \left[\frac{X(z) \cdot z^m}{z^K} \right] \quad (6)$$

110 Figure 3 shows the UWT analysis scheme using CS with maximum decomposition level J . The
111 output of the CS analysis is composed by the wavelet coefficients of M DWT's, so the total number
112 of coefficients is $MK = 2^J K$. The expressions of the CS wavelet coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{m,j}(z) &= X_m(z)[H(z)(2 \downarrow)]^{j-1}[G(z)(2 \downarrow)] \\ a_{m,j}(z) &= X_m(z)[H(z)(2 \downarrow)]^j \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

113 with $0 \leq m \leq M - 1$ and $1 \leq j \leq J$.

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Figure 3. Block diagram of the CS analysis with M shifts.

117 The synthesis of the recovered signal $X_r(z)$ from the CS wavelet coefficients is carried out by
118 means of several parallel iDWT's processes, followed by the inverse shifts that compensate the ones
119 performed during the analysis process (see Figure 4). In this way, if the wavelet coefficients have not
120 been modified, the signals recovered for each shift, $X_{r,m}(z)$, are equal to the original signal $X(z)$. In
121 fact, with the CS method, M processed versions $X_{r,m}(z)$ of the original signal $X(z)$ are obtained.

122 Using the expression (5), $X_{r,m}(z)$ can be written as:

$$X_{r,m}(z) = S_{-m} \left[a_{m,J}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^J + \sum_{j=1}^J d_{m,j}(z)(2 \uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} \right] \quad (8)$$

123 Finally, the recovered signal $X_r(z)$ is obtained by combining the different signals $X_{r,m}(z)$
124 using the mean. The Figure 4 show the complete diagram block of the CS synthesis process.

$$X_r(z) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} X_{r,m}(z) \quad (9)$$

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126
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Figure 4. Block diagram of the CS synthesis with M shifts.

128 An alternative to reduce the number of shifts $M = 2^J$ is the PCS method. The PCS method
 129 introduced in [17-19] is an approximation of the CS method with a reduced the number of shifts,
 130 $M < 2^J$. The PCS method selects a subset of the shifts and performs the UWT in a similar way than
 131 the CS method. The quality of the results obtained with the PCS method depends on the selected
 132 subset of shifts, but with an adequate selection of the shifts the quality of the processed signal is
 133 maintained. The PCS method can obtain good results with $M \cong J$, reducing the number of shifts
 134 from 2^J to J , and obtaining a computational cost reduction by factor of approximately $2^J/J$. The
 135 PCS method optimizes the CS method maintaining the same block diagrams both in analysis and
 136 synthesis, but reducing the number of shifts ($M < 2^J$); the RCS method presented in this work
 137 optimizes the CS method using a new synthesis block diagram with only one iDWT.

138 3. Reduced Cycling Spinning (RCS) method.

139 The CS algorithm needs a high number of DWT's and iDWT's, one DWT and one iDWT for
 140 each signal shift. The number of operations performed in each DWT or iDWT is approximately $2CK$,
 141 being C a constant factor that depends on the filter length and K the number of samples of the
 142 input signal $x(k)$. Thus, for the implementation of the CS method with M shifts the number of
 143 needed operations is approximately $4CKM$, $2CKM$ for the analysis tap and $2CKM$ for the synthesis
 144 tap. If all the possible shifts are performed, $M = K$, the number of operations would be
 145 approximately $4CK^2$. Different methods based on the selection of a limited number of shifts have
 146 been proposed to reduce the order of the CS operations from $O(K^2)$ to $O(K \log_2(K))$ [10, 17, 19].
 147 The proposed RCS method eliminates all iDWT's except one, reducing the operations in the
 148 synthesis from $2CKM$ to $2CK$. The RCS method maintains the CS analysis tap and proposes a new
 149 synthesis process, implying approximately $2CK(M + 1)$ operations. Thus, the RCS method reduces
 150 the number of operations from $4CKM$ to $2CK(M + 1)$, very close to the half value. In addition, the
 151 RCS method can be combined with other approximated CS methods as the ones proposed in [10, 17,
 152 19] increasing the computational cost reduction.

153 In the RCS synthesis the combination of the shifted wavelet coefficients is performed prior to
 154 the iDWT and implies some difficulties. The CS synthesis only needs to perform one inverse shift for
 155 each shift performed in the analysis block, but the RCS synthesis needs to perform several inverse
 156 shifts for each shift performed in the analysis block because the shifts associated to the wavelet
 157 coefficients vary depending on the decomposition levels due to decimators. A shift m in the initial
 158 signal $X(z)$ generates a shift of $m/2$ in the coefficients $d_1(z)$, a shift of $m/2^2$ in the coefficients

159 $d_2(z)$, and in general a shift of $m/2^j$ in the coefficients $d_j(z)$. In this way, to compensate the effects
 160 of a shift m over the wavelet coefficients it is necessary to perform an inverse shift $S_{(\frac{-m}{2^1})}[\]$ for the
 161 scale 1, an inverse shift $S_{(\frac{-m}{2^2})}[\]$ for the scale 2, and in general an inverse shift $S_{(\frac{-m}{2^j})}[\]$ for the scale
 162 j .

$$\begin{aligned} d_{m,j}^s(z) &= S_{(\frac{-m}{2^j})}[d_{m,j}(z)] \\ a_{m,j}^s(z) &= S_{(\frac{-m}{2^j})}[a_{m,j}(z)] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

163 On the other hand, the ratio $m/2^j$ is not integer in all cases and it is necessary to approximate
 164 the fractional shifts to an integer in order to perform the inverse coefficients shifts. The
 165 approximation of $m/2^j$ to an integer is done by rounding that it is an easy operation and minimizes
 166 the maximum rounding shift error.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{d}_{m,j}^s(z) &= S_{\text{round}(\frac{-m}{2^j})}[d_{m,j}(z)] \\ \tilde{a}_{m,j}^s(z) &= S_{\text{round}(\frac{-m}{2^j})}[a_{m,j}(z)] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

167 The rounding shift error assumed doing the approximation of equation (11) is:

$$\varepsilon_{m,j} = \frac{m}{2^j} - \text{round}\left(\frac{m}{2^j}\right) = \frac{c}{2^j} \quad (12)$$

168 being c an integer which value depends on m and varies between $-2^{j-1} + 1$ and 2^{j-1} .

169 The module of the maximum rounding shift error is bounded to $1/2$ for all the scales.

170 The rounding shift error $\varepsilon_{m,j}$ generates another error in the wavelet coefficients proportional to
 171 the $\varepsilon_{m,j}$ value. The approximated shifted coefficients, $\tilde{d}_{m,j}^s(z)$ and $\tilde{a}_{m,j}^s(z)$, can be expressed as the
 172 exact shifted coefficients, $d_{m,j}^s(z)$ and $a_{m,j}^s(z)$, plus an error:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{d}_{m,j}^s(z) &= d_{m,j}^s(z) + e_d(\varepsilon_{m,j}) \\ \tilde{a}_{m,j}^s(z) &= a_{m,j}^s(z) + e_a(\varepsilon_{m,j}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

173 being $e_d(\varepsilon_{m,j})$ and $e_a(\varepsilon_{m,j})$ the errors of the wavelet coefficients.

174 The combination of the shifted coefficients is performed with the mean. Other alternatives for
 175 the combination (maximum and minimum) are evaluated in the experimental part, but results
 176 confirm the mean as the best option. The exact combined coefficients, $d_j(z)$ and $a_j(z)$, that would
 177 be obtained using the exact and unavailable shifted coefficients, $d_{m,j}^s(z)$ and $a_{m,j}^s(z)$, have the
 178 expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} d_j(z) &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} d_{m,j}^s(z) \\ a_j(z) &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} a_{m,j}^s(z) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

179 But in practice the proposed RCS algorithm use the approximated shifted coefficients, $\tilde{d}_{m,j}^s(z)$
 180 and $\tilde{a}_{m,j}^s(z)$, for combination and the resulting approximated combined wavelet coefficients $\tilde{d}_j(z)$
 181 and $\tilde{a}_j(z)$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{d}_j(z) &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \tilde{d}_{m,j}^s(z) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} [d_{m,j}^s(z) + e_d(\varepsilon_{m,j})] = d_j(z) + \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} e_d(\varepsilon_{m,j}) = d_j(z) + \bar{e}_d(\varepsilon_{m,j}) \\ \tilde{a}_j(z) &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \tilde{a}_{m,j}^s(z) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} [a_{m,j}^s(z) + e_a(\varepsilon_{m,j})] = a_j(z) + \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} e_a(\varepsilon_{m,j}) = a_j(z) + \bar{e}_a(\varepsilon_{m,j}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

182 The approximated coefficients $\tilde{d}_j(z)$ and $\tilde{a}_j(z)$ are the exact coefficients $d_j(z)$ and $a_j(z)$ plus
 183 the mean errors of the shifted wavelet coefficients, $\bar{e}_d(\varepsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\varepsilon_{m,j})$. These mean errors depend
 184 on the coefficients values distribution and it is not possible to calculate them in a general way. But,
 185 $\bar{e}_d(\varepsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\varepsilon_{m,j})$ also depend on the mean of the rounding shift error whose value is:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{m,j} = \frac{1}{2^j} \sum_{c=-2^{j-1}+1}^{2^{j-1}} \frac{c}{2^j} = \frac{1}{2^j} \frac{2^{j-1}}{2^j} = \frac{1}{2^{j+1}} \quad (16)$$

186 The mean rounding shift error, $\bar{\epsilon}_{m,j}$, has a low fixed value for each scale and decreases in an
 187 exponential way with the scale resulting negligible for many scales. As $\bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})$
 188 depend on $\bar{\epsilon}_{m,j}$, it is possible to conclude that $\bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})$ also have low values, decrease
 189 in an exponential way with the scale and in many scales are negligible. In this way, the high scales
 190 errors affect a large number of samples of the recovered signals but they are very low, whereas the
 191 low scales errors could be more important but affect only a small number of samples of the
 192 recovered signals.

193 Finally, the signal $\tilde{X}_r(z)$ is recovered from the wavelet coefficients $\tilde{d}_j(z)$ and $\tilde{a}_j(z)$ with a
 194 unique iDWT.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{X}_r(z) &= \tilde{a}_j(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^J + \sum_{j=1}^J \tilde{d}_j(z)(2 \uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} = \\ &= [a_j(z) + \bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})][(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^J + \sum_{j=1}^J [d_j(z) + \bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})](2 \uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} = \\ &= X_r(z) + \bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^J + \sum_{j=1}^J \bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})(2 \uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} = X_r(z) + \delta(z) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

195 The approximated recovered signal $\tilde{X}_r(z)$ is the exact recovered signal, $X_r(z)$, plus an error.
 196 The error in the recovered signal is:

$$\delta(z) = \bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^J + \sum_{j=1}^J \bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})(2 \uparrow)\tilde{G}(z)[(2 \uparrow)\tilde{H}(z)]^{j-1} \quad (18)$$

197 The error $\delta(z)$ depends on $\bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})$, $\bar{e}_d(\epsilon_{m,j})$ and $\bar{e}_a(\epsilon_{m,j})$ depend on $\bar{\epsilon}_{m,j}$ that
 198 has low values; so the error $\delta(z)$ will have low values.

199 Figure 5 displays the block diagram of the complete RCS synthesis using the approximated
 200 wavelet coefficients.

201
 202

Figure 5. Block diagram of the RCS synthesis with M shifts.

203 4. Experimental results

204 The goodness of the proposed RCS method is confirmed by applying RCS to a denoising problem
 205 of ultrasonic signals. In this way, in the following subsections an introduction to the wavelet signal
 206 denoising problem is done, to later describe the ultrasonic experiments carried out and show the
 207 results obtained after performing the experiments.

208 4.1. Signal denoising using CS

209 The denoising of signal using wavelets was introduced by Donoho and Johnstone in different
 210 works [24-26]. The denoising processing with wavelets is divided into three basic steps: the first is the
 211 wavelet coefficients calculation of the signal to denoise, the second is the denoising of the wavelet
 212 coefficients by means of thresholding, and the third is the synthesis of the signal from the processed
 213 coefficients.

214 There are different types of thresholds [27, 28], but the three most commonly used in wavelet
 215 denoising are: the Minimax threshold [24], the Universal threshold [25, 26] and the SURE threshold
 216 [25].

217 The Universal threshold is defined by:

$$T_U = \frac{\text{median}(|d_{m,j}|)}{0,6745} \sqrt{2\ln N_j} \quad (19)$$

218 being N_j is the number of $d_{m,j}$ coefficients at level j

219 The Minimax threshold is:

$$T_{Mm} = \frac{\text{median}(|d_{m,j}|)}{0,6745} \lambda^*(N_j) \quad (20)$$

220 where $\lambda^*(N_j)$ is defined in Table 1 of [24].

221 A risk function is used for the SURE threshold that in the case of soft thresholding [29] follows the
 222 expression:

$$SURE(T; X) = N - 2 \cdot \#\{i: |X_i| \leq T\} + \sum_{i=1}^N [\min(|X_i|, T)]^2 \quad (21)$$

223 being $\#\{i: |X_i| \leq T\}$ the cardinal of $\{i: |X_i| \leq T\}$.

224 The SURE threshold is the value that minimizes:

$$T_S = \arg \min_{T \geq 0} \left\{ SURE \left(T; \frac{d_{m,j}}{\text{median}(|d_{m,j}|)/0,6745} \right) \right\} \quad (22)$$

225 4.2. Experimental setup

226 Several sets of synthetic ultrasonic traces were generated to the experimental verification of the
 227 RCS method. Each synthetic trace was generated by the insertion of a real ultrasonic echo acquired
 228 from a 1 MHz frequency transducer in a simulated ultrasonic grain noise register. The coloured
 229 ultrasonic grain noise registers, $N(f)$, came from a noise simulator based in the model proposed in
 230 [30]:

$$N(f) = [N_1(f)f^2 H_t(f)] \exp(\alpha_0 f^4) + N_2(f) \quad (23)$$

231 where $H_t(f)$ is the frequency response of the ultrasonic transducer, $N_1(f)$ models the structure of the
 232 material, α_0 is the attenuation and $N_2(f)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise associated to the
 233 measuring equipment.

234 The registers corresponding to the ultrasonic echo and the grain noise were added with different
 235 weights to generate several sets of traces with different signal to noise ratios (SNR). The SNR was used
 236 as the quality parameter for both the initial signal and the processed signals. SNR was defined by [28,
 237 30-32]:

$$\text{SNR} = \frac{\text{peak value in target zone}}{\text{standard deviation of trace}} \quad (24)$$

238 7 sets of 1000 traces with different SNR were generated. The length of each trace was $K = 4096$
 239 samples and the sampling frequency was 64 MHz, thus the length of the simulated registers was 64
 240 microseconds. The value of the attenuation parameter of noise was $\alpha_0 = 1,8 \cdot 10^{-26}$.

241 4.3. Experimental results

242 The simulations presented in this paper were done using MATLAB over a Windows PC with
 243 Intel Core i7-4790k CPU and 16MB of RAM. Denoising processing was performed for the 7 sets of
 244 noisy ultrasonic registers with the CS, PCS and RCS method, using CS and PCS as references. For all
 245 methods, Daubechies 6 [2] was selected as mother wavelet due to the previous experience with this
 246 kind of signals [17-20], $J=7$ was the maximum decomposition level, the filters border treatment was
 247 zero padding and soft thresholding was used with threshold values calculated independently for each
 248 decomposition level [27]. RCS was applied in combination with the PCS method to obtain a greater
 249 reduction of the computational cost. The number of shifts used for both the RCS and the PCS methods
 250 was $M=8$, the selected shifts values for the two methods were $m \in \{3, 14, 51, 61, 88, 97, 104, 108\}$.
 251 Three evaluations were carried out varying the threshold: Minimax, Sure and Universal. Additionally,
 252 in the RCS method three alternatives for the combination of the wavelet coefficients were studied:
 253 mean, maximum and minimum.

254 Two types of results were obtained: numerical and graphical. The numerical results are displayed
 255 in Tables 1, 2 and 3 where the mean SNR values of the 7 sets of 1000 ultrasonic traces processed with
 256 different methods are listed. The Tables 1, 2 and 3 contain 6 columns and the differences among tables
 257 are due to the threshold utilized in the denoising. The first column values are common for the three
 258 tables and correspond to the initial SNR of the ultrasonic traces. The columns two and three show the
 259 reference results obtained using the CS and PCS methods and the three last columns list the SNR
 260 values using the RCS method with the three combination choices: mean, minimum and maximum.

261 Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the SNR results of the CS, PCS and RCS methods are similar. Although the
 262 RCS method was proposed using the mean for the coefficients combination, the SNR results using the
 263 minimum and the maximum are close to the mean results and even in some cases they are slightly
 264 better. But the mean choice generates registers in which the non-eliminated noise peaks are lower than
 265 in the minimum and maximum cases, even lower than in the CS and PCS cases.

266 **Table 1.** SNR mean of 1000 ultrasonic traces sets after denoising with different methods using
 267 Universal threshold.

Initial	CS	PCS	RCS mean	RCS max.	RCS min.
3,09	0,91	0,92	0,93	0,68	1,24
3,89	2,81	2,67	2,70	1,881	3,46
4,74	6,53	6,39	6,36	5,11	6,65
5,61	8,91	8,88	8,81	8,54	8,74
6,49	9,36	9,28	9,27	9,48	9,40
7,33	9,28	9,29	9,31	9,39	9,50
8,13	9,02	8,92	8,94	9,17	9,18

268 **Table 2.** SNR mean of 1000 ultrasonic traces sets after denoising with different methods using
 269 Minimax threshold.

Initial	CS	PCS	RCS mean	RCS max.	RCS min.
3,09	3,31	3,04	2,83	2,97	3,74
3,89	6,42	6,34	6,28	5,95	6,48
4,74	8,59	8,54	8,50	7,88	8,43
5,61	9,12	8,94	8,94	8,96	9,19
6,49	9,14	8,99	8,97	9,15	9,18
7,33	9,03	8,91	8,92	9,12	9,17
8,13	8,84	8,80	8,80	9,06	9,14

270
271**Table 3.** SNR mean of 1000 ultrasonic traces sets after denoising with different methods using Sure threshold.

Initial	CS	PCS	RCS mean	RCS max.	RCS min.
3,09	3,79	3,72	3,67	3,20	4,05
3,89	6,10	6,05	6,03	5,45	5,95
4,74	7,62	7,61	7,58	6,86	7,42
5,61	8,28	8,26	8,25	7,90	8,29
6,49	8,54	8,50	8,51	8,30	8,53
7,33	8,64	8,56	8,57	8,65	8,74
8,13	8,64	8,61	8,62	8,75	8,79

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Figure 6. Ultrasonic traces after denoising with different methods using a soft Minimax threshold: (a) Ultrasonic pulse and initial trace with noise, SNR= 4.24 and MSE=0.0413; (b) Denoised trace with CS method, SNR= 9.08 and MSE=0.0072; (c) Denoised trace with PCS method using 8 shifts, SNR= 8.18 and MSE=0.0066; (d) Denoised trace with RCS method using 8 shifts and mean to combine coefficients, SNR= 8.26 and MSE=0.0062; (e) Denoised trace with RCS method using 8 shifts and minimum to combine coefficients, SNR= 8.25 and MSE=0.0086; (f) Denoised trace with RCS method using 8 shifts and maximum to combine coefficients, SNR= 7.95 and MSE=0.0092.

282 Figures 6(b-e) show the normalized graphical results of the denoised ultrasonic trace with noise of
 283 Figure 6(a) with different wavelet methods using the Minimax threshold. The processed signals of
 284 Figures 6(c-f) were processed using the same 8 shifts and have a SNR very close to 8.2. But it can be
 285 clearly observed that Figure 6(d), obtained with RCS and mean, shows lower noise peaks values
 286 outside the area of the recovered pulse than in Figures 6(e) and 6(f). Even, these non-eliminated noise
 287 peaks are also lower in the Figure 6(d) than in Figures 6(b) and 6(c) obtained using CS and PCS
 288 respectively. This noise peaks reduction effect is another improvement observed in the denoising RCS
 289 method with coefficients combination using the mean. The cause of the noise peak reduction has not
 290 been determined with detail and probably it is due to the averaging of the wavelet coefficients, this is
 291 an open problem for a future research.

292 An additional quality parameter was calculated to evaluate the similitude between the denoised
 293 signals of Figures 6 (b-e) and the ultrasonic pulse without noise of Figure 6(a), the Minimum Square
 294 Error (MSE) defined as:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (\tilde{x}_r(k) - P(k))^2 \quad (25)$$

295 being $\tilde{x}_r(k)$ the recovered denoised signal and $P(k)$ the ultrasonic pulse without noise.

296 The MSE of the initial trace with noise (Figure 6(a)) is 0.0413 and it is reduced after the denoising
 297 by all the methods. The best MSE after denoising is obtained, again, by the RCS method with mean
 298 (MSE=0.0062), even this value is slightly better than MSE PCS value (MSE=0.0066) and MSE CS value
 299 (MSE=0.0072). The RCS methods with minimum and maximum have MSE values of 0.0086 and 0.0092
 300 respectively.

301 Figure 7 shows the joint comparison of the denoised ultrasonic registers of Figure 6 (b), (c), (d)
 302 and (e). The individual curves are yet shown in the Figure 6. In Figure 7 the curves are superposed to
 303 compare the reduction of the residual noise and the perfect synchronisation of the recovered signals.
 304 To evaluate the residual noise in Figure 7, the curves are ordered according to the noise level; the curve
 305 with the greatest residual noise (RCS with minimum) is represented at the deepest level whereas the
 306 curve with the lowest residual noise (RCS with mean) is represented at the most superficial level. In
 307 Figure 7 the green line corresponds to the RCS method with mean and shows the lowest values in the
 308 noise peaks. The highest values of the noise peaks correspond to RCS method using minimum (black
 309 line), whereas the registers associate to CS and PCS have intermediate values. Additionally, Figure 7
 310 shows the perfect time synchronization achieved in the recovered signals using the RCS method. The
 311 perfect time synchronization and the low values of the residual noise confirm the goodness of the RCS
 312 method.

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Figure 7. Comparative of denoised ultrasonic traces with four methods using a soft Minimax threshold.

316 4.4. Error evaluation.

317 Another experiment was designed to evaluate the influence of the rounding shift error over the
 318 recovered signal. In this experiment only the RCS analysis and synthesis of an ultrasonic pulse were
 319 performed (without the denoising), and the initial and the recovered pulses were compared. In the
 320 RCS synthesis part, the rounding shift error for all the scales was selected equal to 1/2, this error
 321 corresponds to the theoretical worse case and it cannot happen in a real problem because there is not a
 322 shift that generates rounding shift errors equal to 1/2 for all the scales.

323 The simulation used Daubechies 6, $J=7$ and zero padding as in the previous denoising
 324 experiments. To simplify the representation but without loss of generality, the shifts $m = 0$ and
 325 $m = 1$ were selected to calculate the RCS analysis wavelet coefficients and to generate the RCS shifted
 326 wavelet coefficients with rounding shift errors. In this way, the shifted wavelet coefficients with
 327 rounding shift error equal to 1/2 for all the scales were obtained using:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{d}_{0,j}^s(z) &= d_{0,j}^s(z) + \frac{d_{0,j}^s(z) - d_{1,j}^s(z)}{2} \\ \tilde{a}_{0,j}^s(z) &= a_{0,j}^s(z) + \frac{a_{0,j}^s(z) - a_{1,j}^s(z)}{2}\end{aligned}\quad (26)$$

328 Note that a rounding shift error equal to 1/2 implies the error of the shifted wavelet coefficients
 329 correspond to a half of the difference between the wavelet coefficients of two consecutive shifts, 0 and
 330 1 in the present case.

331 **Figure 8.** Effects of a rounding shift error equal to 1/2 in all the scales. (a) Ultrasonic pulse to analyse and to
 332 synthesize; (b) Wavelet coefficients with $m = 0$; (c) Approximated shifted wavelet coefficients (with rounding
 333 shift error influence) for scales $j = 4, 5, 6$ and 7 , and error of the wavelet coefficients; (d) Recovered pulse after
 334 RCS analysis and synthesis, and difference between pulses of Figures 8(a) and 8(d).

335 Figure 8 shows the initial and the recovered pulses, the wavelet coefficients and the errors
 336 committed during the RCS process in both wavelet coefficients and recovered pulse. Figure 8(a)
 337 displays the initial ultrasonic pulse. Figure 8(b) represents the wavelet coefficients of the ultrasonic
 338 pulse, in this figure it can be appreciated that the coefficients are different to 0 only in scales $j =$
 339 4, 5, 6 and 7. Figure 8(c) shows the scales $j = 4, 5, 6$ and 7 of the approximated shifted wavelet
 340 coefficients and the error associated to each approximated shifted wavelet coefficient. In this figure it
 341 can be appreciated the low magnitude of the wavelet coefficients error. Figure 8(d) contains the curves
 342 of the recovered pulse and the difference (error) between the initial pulse and the recovered pulse. In
 343 this figure it can be observed the low magnitude of the error in the recovered pulse. A MSE of $3.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
 344 confirms the low magnitude of the error in the recovered pulse.

345 A second experiment was designed to evaluate the errors in the RCS method with real shifts. In
 346 this experiment the ultrasonic pulse was analysed and synthesized with the set of shifts used in the
 347 denoising experiment, $m \in \{3, 14, 51, 61, 88, 97, 104, 108\}$. The rounding shift errors $\varepsilon_{m,j}$ associated to
 348 each shift m and scale j are listed in the Table 4. The mean of the rounding shift errors associated to
 349 each scale is in all the scales inferior to the $1/2$ value used in the previous error evaluation.

350 **Table 4.** Rounding shift error $\varepsilon_{m,j}$ for $m \in \{3, 14, 51, 61, 88, 97, 104, 108\}$ and $J = 7$.

m	$j=1$	$j=2$	$j=3$	$j=4$	$j=5$	$j=6$	$j=7$
3	1/2	-1/4	3/8	3/16	3/32	3/64	3/128
14	0	2/4	-2/8	-2/16	14/32	14/64	14/128
51	1/2	-1/4	3/8	3/16	-13/32	-13/64	51/128
61	1/2	1/4	-3/8	-3/16	-3/32	-3/64	61/128
88	0	0	0	8/16	-8/32	24/64	-40/128
97	1/2	1/4	1/8	1/16	1/32	-31/64	-31/128
104	0	0	0	8/16	8/32	-24/64	-24/128
108	0	0	4/8	-4/16	12/32	-20/64	-20/128
mean	1/4	2/16	3/32	9/64	7/128	25/256	7/512

351
 352 Figure 9(a) displays the approximated shifted wavelet coefficients and its error. As in figure 8(c),
 353 they are only represented the scales $j = 4, 5, 6$ and 7 with coefficients values different to 0. The
 354 magnitude of the coefficients error of Figure 9(a) is inferior to the magnitude of the coefficients error of
 355 Figure 8(a). Figure 9(b) shows the recovered pulse and the error of the recovered pulse. The error of
 356 the recovered pulse is also inferior to the error in Figure 8(d); the MSE in this case is $1.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$.

357 Two experiments have been performed to evaluate the errors in the RCS method. The first
 358 experiment simulates the theoretical and non-real case where the rounding shift error is maximum
 359 ($1/2$) for all the scales; the second experiment corresponds to the set of shifts used in the denoising
 360 problem. Both experiments confirm that although the error associated to the recovery signal using RCS
 361 method depends on each specific signal, the magnitudes of the errors is low compared with the
 362 magnitudes of the shifted wavelet coefficients and the recovered signal. Also the MSE values confirm
 363 the low magnitude of the errors.

364

365 **Figure 9.** Effects of the rounding shift error with $m \in \{3, 14, 51, 61, 88, 97, 104, 108\}$. (a) Approximated shifted
 366 wavelet coefficients for scales $j = 4, 5, 6$ and 7 and error of the wavelet coefficients; (b) Recovered pulse after
 367 RCS analysis and synthesis, and difference between pulses of Figures 8(a) and 9(b).
 368

369 5. Conclusions

370 This paper introduces the RCS method for the CS-UWT implementation that reduces the
 371 computational cost by a factor close to 2 and is compatible with other optimized methods as PCS.
 372 The proposed RCS method maintains the analysis blocks of the CS method but changes the synthesis
 373 tap reducing the number of iDWT's to one. For the iDWT's reduction in the synthesis tap, it is
 374 necessary to perform a combination over the wavelet coefficients, instead of over the recovered
 375 signals as in the CS method.

376 The combination of the wavelet coefficients associated to each shift has implied the proposal of
 377 solutions to the difficulties appeared during the development. The main difficulty was due to the
 378 fact that the shifts have integer values in the shifted signals, but not in the CS wavelet coefficients
 379 because the decimation process. To solve this problem and calculate the inverse shifts during the
 380 synthesis process, the shifts were rounded and a rounding shift error was generated. The rounding
 381 shift error was studied and its effects over the recovered signal were estimated. The error in the
 382 recovered signal depends on the mean value of the rounding shift error, and the mean value of the
 383 rounding shift error has been calculated resulting $\bar{\epsilon}_{m,j} = \frac{1}{2^{j+1}}$. So, the error in the recovered signal is
 384 proportional to $\frac{1}{2^{j+1}}$, negligible in most of the samples; the experimental results confirm this
 385 hypothesis.

386 The novelty of the proposed RCS method is the combination of the wavelet coefficients
 387 associated with each shift, so different alternatives for the coefficients combination have been
 388 studied. Specifically, the paper shows results using three alternatives for the coefficients
 389 combination: the mean, the maximum and the minimum. In denoising processing applications, the
 390 SNR and MSE values do not show big differences among the coefficients combination methods.

391 On the other hand the graphical results of denoised ultrasonic traces show an interesting effect,
 392 the non-eliminated noise peaks are smaller using the RCS method with the mean than using RCS
 393 with the minimum or maximum. Also, there is a reduction of these noise peaks compared with the
 394 CS and PCS methods. The reduction of the non-eliminated noise peaks in RCS denoising must be
 395 studied to determinate the causes and to evaluate the effects of applying RCS to other signal
 396 processing problems.

397 The final conclusion is that this work introduces the RCS method for the CS UWT
 398 implementation with the half computational cost of the standard CS method, develops the RCS
 399 mathematical formulation, shows the block diagrams of the RCS analysis and synthesis taps,
 400 performs an experimental validation applying the RCS method to an ultrasonic denoising problem
 401 and evaluates the RCS errors.
 402

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405

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407

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